

The mediating role of cognitive flexibility in the relationship between computational thinking and design thinking among students at the college of information technology

Fayeq Rheid Mohammed ¹

¹ Department of Educational and Psychological Sciences, College of Education for Human Sciences, University of Babylon, Iraq

Abstract

Thinking is essential in the age of informatics for individuals and communities seeking to improve their lives and understand the world around them. The objective of this study is to determine the statistical significance of the correlations between computational thinking, cognitive flexibility, and design thinking among students in the college of information technology. The study examines the direct, indirect, and total effects between these three variables. A descriptive approach was used for this research, and data was collected from 378 male and female university students. The researcher utilized various statistical methods to assess the validity and reliability of the tools used. The findings of the study are explained in accordance with the theoretical framework and previous research.

Keywords: Computational thinking; cognitive flexibility; design thinking; mediating role; college of information technology

INTRODUCTION

In light of the qualitative knowledge revolution, we are currently experiencing in the field of technology, individuals are being exposed to a vast amount of diverse information and knowledge. This exposure also allows for the integration of different cultures. As a result, educational institutions must respond positively to these variables, their interactions, and complexities. They should focus on efficiently preparing students, emphasizing thinking skills, and cultivating a high level of ability and capability. This will enable students to actively contribute to the development and well-being of their society. It is the responsibility of everyone involved in the educational process to fulfill this task (Miller et al., 2014).

Walliman (2015) identified a problem in the educational process: many thinking skills, such as computational thinking, are not effectively taught at the university level. Therefore, there is a need for scientific research to uncover and develop these skills. This research would enable students to think logically and sequentially when they encounter problems, using computational thinking as a problem-solving method and acquiring the necessary knowledge (Walliman, 2015).

This compels individuals to develop cognitive flexibility, which involves adapting to new educational conditions and situations by comparing them to previous experiences, simplifying complex ones, and recognizing the familiar as ordinary. Students often adapt to these circumstances in a routine manner, despite the fact that their reality necessitates dealing with complexity. Design thinking emphasizes the generation of multiple ideas, the creation of prototypes, and the sharing of design concepts with others. This approach facilitates the integration of various dimensions of a single concept, enabling learners to comprehend topics comprehensively and meaningfully. It also empowers them to apply their knowledge to solve real-world problems that are relevant to their own experiences. By understanding facts, concepts, principles, and scientific laws through a conscious process, learners can effectively respond to the demands of the digital age and knowledge management. In light of these considerations, there are two primary objectives to be addressed:

Corresponding Author

Fayeq Rheid Mohammed, University of Babylon, Iraq

E-mail: hum.fayeq.rheid@uobabylon.edu.iq

Received : 25 August 2023

Accepted : 10 November 2023

Online Published : 29 December 2023

©2023 JSER, Available online at

<https://www.journalser.com>

Cite this article as: Rheid Mohammed, F. (2023). The mediating role of mental flexibility in the relationship between computational thinking and design thinking among students at the college of information technology. *Journal of Social and Educational Research*, 2(2), 61-67. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10441862>

1. The statistical significance of the correlations between computational thinking, cognitive flexibility, and design thinking among students at the College of Information Technology

2. Direct, indirect, and total effects of the relationships between computational thinking, cognitive flexibility, and design thinking among students at the College of Information Technology

Theoretical framework

Computational thinking

Computational thinking was initially defined by Wing (2006) as the process of problem-solving, system design, and understanding human behavior by utilizing fundamental concepts from computer science. The introduction of computational thinking has strengthened problem-solving methods and integrated it into various disciplines such as mathematics, sciences, statistics, biology, physics, nanotechnology, chemistry, economics, arts, engineering, design, and social sciences (Bundy, 2007; Phillips, 2009). Currently, there is a growing recognition among researchers regarding the significance of computational thinking as a crucial skill for individuals in the twenty-first century. This importance extends to students, regardless of whether they specialize in computer science or not (Easterbrook, 2014; Django, 2016; Voogt et al., 2015).

Paka et al. (2019) and Korucu et al. (2017) support Wing's definition and emphasize that computational thinking involves creative thinking (Korucu et al., 2017; Paka et al., 2019). The National Research Council of the USA (NRC) (2010) defines computational thinking (CT) as a collection of ideas, strategies, and mental habits that can be applied to problem-solving (Haseski et al., 2018). Doleck et al., (2017) state that computational thinking is an overarching term encompassing various cognitive skills, including design thinking, creative thinking, critical and analytical thinking, and cognitive thinking (Doleck et al., 2017).

Students in the field of information technology need to have computational thinking as a vital skill in their studies and work. Romero et al., (2017) agree with Doleck et al., (2017) that computational thinking involves cognitive and metacognitive strategies, where learners actively participate in the design and creation process (Romero et al., 2017). According to Phillips (2009), computational thinking is a thinking pattern that revolves around understanding the nature of information, its purpose, availability, acquisition, interpretation, analysis, storage, usage, and accessibility, as well as the ability to generate new information using computational methods (Phillips, 2009). Basawapatna (2013) explains that computational thinking encompasses a set of thought processes related to essential computer skills, such as problem formulation, logical information organization, algorithmic thinking for automating solutions, and abstraction for representing and summarizing information (Basawapatna, 2013). On the other hand, the American Association of Computer Science Teachers (CSTA), in collaboration with the

International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE), provides a description of computational thinking as a problem-solving method that includes various characteristics, not limited to the following:

- Formulate problems in a way that enables the use of computers and other tools to assist in solving them.
- Organize information logically and analyze it.
- Represent information through models and simulations.
- Automate solutions through algorithmic thinking.
- Identify, analyze, and implement potential solutions to achieve the most efficient and effective combination of steps and resources for problem-solving.
- Generalize and apply the problem-solving process to a wide range of problems (Computer Science Teachers Association, 2011).

Grover (2018) emphasizes the importance of higher-level thinking when addressing life's challenges. This involves a series of steps that both humans and machines can follow to comprehend the problem, analyze it, and formulate a solution that can be understood and applied by both parties (Grover, 2018). Computational thinking goes beyond the conventional notion of computer skills, which pertains to the proficient use of technology. It is grounded in several key principles, including abstraction, which simplifies information and details to focus on concepts that aid in understanding and problem-solving. Additionally, it facilitates information in the process of knowledge formation, and digital devices, systems, and interconnected networks facilitate problem-solving. Computational thinking fosters creativity in various fields, including natural sciences, social sciences, humanities, medicine, arts, engineering, and business administration. Lastly, it involves developing tools and expressing solutions to problems mathematically in certain domains (Weinberg, 2013).

Characteristics of computational thinking

Barr and Stephenson (2011) argue that students live and work in a technology-driven world. They state that computational thinking is a problem-solving process that includes the following characteristics:

- Organize and analyze information logically.
- Information modeling, abstraction and simulation.
- Identify, test and implement possible solutions.
- Automation of solutions by algorithmic thinking.
- Generalization of this process and its application to other issues.
- Confidence in dealing with complex situations.
- Constancy in working with difficult problems.
- Formulate problems in a way that enables the use of computers and other tools to help solve them (Barr & Stephenson, 2011).

(Wing, 2006) defined the general characteristics of computational thinking as follows:

- Focus on concepts, not programming.
- Computational thinking is a fundamental skill, not a repetitive task.
- Computational thinking mirrors human thinking, not computer thinking.
- Computational thinking encompasses mathematical and engineering thinking skills.
- Computational thinking emphasizes ideas, not tools.
- Computational thinking is beneficial for everyone, regardless of location (Wing, 2006).

Design thinking

According to Barry and Beckman (2007), Design Thinking is the process of using tools and practices to develop new practical and creative products and solutions. Its purpose is to address problems and fulfill the needs and desires of society, enabling innovation in design (Beckman & Barry, 2007).

Brown (2008) explains that design thinking is a non-linear methodology comprising five elements. It starts with empathy and concludes with testing. These elements are integrated and coordinated into a strategy applied to societal problems across different fields. Design thinking is a human-centered approach that emphasizes using empathy and understanding to design experiences that foster active participation. It not only seeks new solutions to existing problems but also identifies new problems to solve (Brown, 2008).

Carroll et al., (2011) noted that teachers and learners in classrooms apply design thinking by creating pre-designed study models using computer or digital technologies as social cognitive tools. This approach allows individuals with problem-solving skills to develop models that simplify the complexity of the problem. Eventually, these models can be fully described by digital applications in the classroom. The authors then proceeded to outline the methodology and applications of design thinking in education as follows:

- Integrate the methodology of design thinking in the education of engineering, computer and digital technologies.
- Development of innovation among learners.
- Development of creative thinking, design and graphic skills.
- It develops a positive attitude among learners towards problem-solving activities and building participatory solutions.
- It develops a positive attitude among learners towards learning, by changing their behavior and responses (Carroll et al., 2010).

Other studies (Kumar, 2017) (Lindberg et al., 2011) suggest that the application of design thinking improves the innovation, development, and utilization of digital and computer technologies among students at school levels. This is achieved through collaborative work and the creation of model solutions in a participatory manner within a team (Kumar, 2017; Lindberg et al., 2011).

Cognitive flexibility as a mediator

Cognitive flexibility is a necessary requirement for individuals in our current time to effectively navigate different situations. They must be able to adapt their thinking and smoothly transition from one idea to another as needed. According to Dibbets et al. (2006), cognitive flexibility involves the ability to generate diverse ideas and adjust mental orientation in response to the situation (Dibbets et al., 2006). Shah (2003) further defines cognitive flexibility as the ability to rapidly generate ideas and change mental attitudes in response to new stimuli (Shah, 2003).

As for Deak (2003), he believes that cognitive flexibility is the continuous construction and modification of cognitive representations. It involves generating solutions based on the available information in the environment. When faced with a problem that has a wide range of solutions, a flexible individual builds new cognitive representation or modifies existing ones to narrow down the possible responses. This allows them to generate new responses based on the information available in the environment (Deak, 2003).

Rose (2011) explains that cognitive flexibility is the ability to build knowledge in different and diverse ways, enhancing adaptation to learning situations (Rose, 2011).

Anderson (2002) explains that cognitive flexibility refers to an individual's ability to move and adapt to a specific situation that requires problem-solving. It involves transitioning from one idea to another easily and effortlessly, allowing the individual to consider the problem from multiple perspectives (Anderson, 2002).

Dillon and Vineyard (1999) identified the third components of cognitive flexibility, namely

- Flexible coding: refers to the ability of an individual to encode the stimulus in several meanings
- Flexible grouping: the ability of an individual to generate multiple tactics for solving through the use of inductive thinking, which depends on the available elements in order to reach a solution
- Flexible comparison: the ability of an individual to change tactical solutions whenever there is a change in the tasks, where he chooses certain elements for the solution, and compare them with several other elements in order to change tactical solutions (Dillon & Vineyard, 1999).

METHODS

Participant and procedure

Associative research was used to design this study. To choose the research sample, the researcher utilized a basic random approach with a proportionate distribution. Students from the University of Babylon's Faculty of Information Technology made up the sample. For the third and fourth stages, there were 113 male students, accounting for 51% of the sample, and 107 female students, accounting for 49% of the sample. The average age of the sample was 21.3. The data was collected voluntarily,

and no costs were charged for participation. Participants were informed that they might opt out of the study at any point.

Measures

Computational Thinking Scale (CTS)

The researcher adapting Computational Thinking Scale (CTS) from Korkmaz and Bai (2019) study. The scale, which consists of (20) items measuring five dimensions, is answered in a 5-point Likert type (1= never and 5= always). It can be said that the reliability (Cronbach alpha: 0.86) and validity can be shown in Table 1 of the scale are in the acceptable range.

Scale	χ^2/df	RMSEA	RMR	GFI	AGFI	CFI	IFI	TLI
CTS	2.266	0.076	0.107	0.95	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.90
DTS	1.356	0.040	0.072	0.92	0.90	0.93	0.93	0.91
CFS	3.524	0.07	0.113	0.87	0.82	0.81	0.81	0.77

Note. CTS Computational Thinking Scale; DTS Design Thinking Scale; CFS Cognitive Flexibility Scale

Design Thinking Scale

The researcher adapting Tsai Design Thinking Scale from Tsai (2018) study. The scale, which consists of (16) items, is answered in a 5-point Likert type (1= Strongly disagree and 5= Strongly agree). It can be said that the reliability (Cronbach alpha: 0.80) and validity can be shown in Table 1 of the scale are in the acceptable range.

Cognitive Flexibility Scale

The researcher adapting Cognitive Flexibility Scale from martin & Rubin (1995) study. The scale, which consists of (12) items, is answered in a 6-point Likert type (1= Strongly disagree and 6= Strongly agree). It can be said that the reliability (Cronbach alpha: 0.82) and validity can be shown in Table 1 of the scale are in the acceptable range.

RESULTS

The data were analyzed using SPSS 24 and Amos. The aims is:

1. The statistical significance of the correlations between computational thinking, cognitive flexibility, and design thinking among students at the College of Information Technology

Correlation analysis indicated (see Table 2) that cognitive flexibility was positively correlated with both design thinking, and computational thinking. Skewness and kurtosis values were within the normality criteria.

Variable	Descriptive Statistics				Correlations		
	M	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	CT	DT	CF
CT	71.78	12.00	-0.537	1.452	–		
DT	57.38	9.38	-0.424	0.31	.563**	–	
CF	49.15	6.04	0.362	0.562	.247**	.313**	–

Note. ** $p < .01$, CT Computational thinking; DT Design thinking; CF Cognitive flexibility

2. Direct, indirect, and total effects of the relationships between computational thinking, cognitive flexibility, and design

thinking among students at the College of Information Technology

The mediation analysis revealed a statistically significant indirect association between computational thinking and design thinking, mediated by cognitive flexibility (see Table 3 and Figure 1).

Figure 1. The result of mediational model

Path	Direct Effects	Indirect Effects	Total Effects	C.R.	t test
CT → CF	0.124	0	0.124	3.774*	1.96
CF → DT	0.228	0	0.288	9.204*	
CT → DT	0.404	0.036	0.44	3.297*	

Note. * C.R. < t test tabulated value (1.96)

From observing the table above, we find that all critical ratio values (C.R.) are significant when compared to the tabular value of (1.96) at a significance level of (0.05).

DISCUSSION

In this study, the relationship between computational thinking and design thinking and the mediating role of cognitive flexibility in this relationship were examined. The findings are discussed below in light of the literature, respectively.

The first finding of the study is that there is a positive and substantial association between computational thinking, design thinking, and cognitive flexibility. This association could be the result of Mental flexibility is the ability to think about a problem in various ways and come up with unique solutions. Computational thinking is the capacity to solve problems by breaking things down into smaller parts and employing algorithms. Design thinking is a problem-solving approach that includes analyzing the user's needs, developing solutions, prototyping and testing various ideas. Mental flexibility, computational thinking, and design thinking are all critical abilities for success in today's environment, with research indicating a favorable association between the two. Design thinking and computational thinking are ontological mirror processes., and are the two processes by which thinkers address problems (Kelly & Gero, 2021).

Computational thinking is the ability to solve problems by breaking them down into smaller parts and employing algorithms, according to the study's second finding. The ability to think about a problem in multiple ways and come up with creative solutions is referred to as mental flexibility. Design thinking is a problem-solving approach that includes analyzing the user's needs, developing solutions, prototyping and testing various ideas.

As a result, computational thinking may be able to predict design thinking through the mediation of mental flexibility. This suggests that computational thinking is a necessary talent for design thinking, and mental flexibility is a skill that aids in the development of computational thinking skills (Garay & Quintana, 2021).

A growing body of evidence suggests that there is a link between computational thinking, mental flexibility, and design thinking. Students who were taught computational thinking skills improved their mental flexibility and design thinking skills, according to one study. Another study discovered that students who were taught computational thinking skills were more likely to come up with creative solutions to problems. These studies suggest that computational thinking can be a useful tool for developing mental flexibility and design thinking skills (Paf & Dinçer, 2021).

Implications

This study suggests that there may be a synergistic relationship between computational thinking, design thinking, and mental flexibility. In other words, learning about one of these skills may help students learn about the others. This is significant because it suggests that teaching these skills together may be more effective than teaching them separately.

In addition to the research studies conducted on the relationship between computational thinking, design thinking, and mental flexibility, there are also numerous anecdotal reports from teachers and educators who have witnessed the benefits of teaching these skills together. For instance, a teacher reported that her students, who were taught computational thinking and design thinking, displayed higher levels of engagement in learning and were more inclined to generate innovative solutions to problems.

Overall, research findings and anecdotal reports suggest that there is a relationship between computational thinking, design thinking, and mental flexibility. This implies that teaching these skills together may be more effective than teaching them separately.

Conclusion

As a result, it has been revealed that mental flexibility plays a full mediator role in the relationship between computational thinking and design thinking. Additionally, the study highlights the direct relationships between computational thinking, design thinking, and mental flexibility. The findings suggest that

computational thinking has a direct effect on mental flexibility, with a significant direct effect value of 3.774 compared to the tabulated t-value of 1.96 at a significant level of 0.05. This indicates that changes in mental flexibility occur directly due to computational thinking. Furthermore, computational thinking has both a direct and indirect impact on design thinking, with a significant direct and indirect effect value of 9.204 compared to the tabulated t-value of 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05. The study also found that computational thinking has a direct impact on design thinking, with a significant direct effect value of 3.297 compared to the tabulated t-value of 1.96 at a significant level of 0.05. This suggests that changes in design thinking occur directly and indirectly as a result of computational thinking.

Funding. The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Availability of Data and Material. Data will be available on request.

Informed Consent: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Peer-review: Externally peer-reviewed.

Financial Disclosure: No financial disclosure was received.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, P. (2002). Assessment and development of executive function (EF) during childhood. *Child Neuropsychology*, 8(2), 71–82. <https://doi.org/10.1076/chin.8.2.71.8724>
- Basawapatna, A., Koh, K. H., Repenning, A., Webb, D. C., & Marshall, K. S. (2011). Recognizing computational thinking patterns. *Proceedings of the 42nd ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1953163.1953241>
- Barr, V., & Stephenson, C. (2011). Bringing computational thinking to K-12. *ACM Inroads*, 2(1), 48–54. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1929887.1929905>
- Beckman, S. L., & Barry, M. (2007). Innovation as a learning process: Embedding design thinking. *California Management Review*, 50(1), 25–56. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41166415>
- Brown, T. (2008). Design thinking. *Harvard Business Review*, 86(6), 84–92.
- Bundy, A. (2007). Computational thinking is pervasive. *Journal of Scientific and Practical Computing*, 1(2), 67–69.
- Carroll, M., Goldman, S., Britos, L., Koh, J., Royalty, A., & Hornstein, M. (2010). Destination, imagination and the

- fires within: design thinking in a middle school classroom. *International Journal of Art & Design Education*, 29(1), 37–53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-8070.2010.01632.x>
- Deák, G. (2003). The development of cognitive flexibility and language abilities. *Advances in Child Development and Behavior*, 31, 271-327. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2407\(03\)31007-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2407(03)31007-9).
- Dede, C., Mishra, P., & Voogt, J. (2013). Working Group 6: Advancing computational thinking in 21st century learning. *Paper presented at EDU summit 2013, International summit on ICT in education*, Washington, USA.
- Design Thinking, a guide for modeling and testing SDG solutions. UNDP (2017).
- Dibbets, P. & Jolles, J. (2006). The Switch Task for Children: Measuring mental flexibility in young children. *Cognitive Development*, 21, 60-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2005.09.004>.
- Dillon, R. & Vineyard, G. (1999). *Cognitive flexibility. further validation of flexible combination*, Retrieved 15/8/2014, Available from <http://www.eric.ed.gov>.
- Djambong, T. (2016). Computational thinking in connection with the acquisition of key for the 21st century. Reflection from literature, *Proceedings of EDULEARN16 Conference 4th-6th July 2016, Barcelona, Spain*.
- Doleck, T., Bazelais, P., Lemay, D. J., Saxena, A., & Basnet, R. B. (2017). Algorithmic thinking, cooperativity, creativity, critical thinking, and problem solving: Exploring the relationship between computational thinking skills and academic performance. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 4(4), 355–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-017-0090-9>
- Easterbrook, S.M. (2014). *From computational thinking to systems thinking: A conceptual toolkit for sustainability computing*. ICT for Sustainability.
- Grover, Shuchi & Pea, Roy. (2017). Computational thinking: A competency whose time has come. *Computer Science Education: Perspectives on Teaching and Learning in School*, 19–38. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781350057142.ch-003>
- Haseski, H., Ilic, U. & Tugtekin, U. (2018). Defining a new 21st century skill-computational thinking: Concepts and trends. *International Education Studies*, 11-29. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v11n4p29>.
- Kelly, N. & Gero, J. (2021). Design thinking and computational thinking. a dual process model for addressing design problems. *Design Science*. <https://doi.org/7.10.1017/dsj.2021.7>
- Korucu, A. T., Gencturk, A. T. & Gundogdu, M. M. (2017). Examination of the computational thinking skills of students. *Journal of Learning and Teaching in Digital Age*, 2(1), 11-19.
- Kules, B. (2016). Computational thinking is critical thinking: Connecting to university discourse, goals, and learning outcomes. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 53, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pra2.2016.14505301092>
- Kumar, V. (2017). *Design thinking vs computational thinking in education*. <https://blog.quicksense.org/design-thinking-vs-computational-thinking-in-education-2dcf5b23aa12>
- Lindberg, T., Meinel, C., & Wagner, R. (2011). Design thinking: A fruitful concept for it development? *Design Thinking* https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-13757-0_1
- Martin, M., & Rubin, R. (1995). A new measure of cognitive flexibility. *Psychological Reports*, 623-626. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.1995.76.2.623>
- Miller, L. D., Soh, L., Chiriacescu, V., Ingraham, E., Shell, D., & Hazley, M. (2014). Integrating computational and creative thinking to improve learning and performance in CS1. SIGCSE 2014 - *Proceedings of the 45th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education*. 475-480. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2538862.2538940>.
- Paf, M., & Dinçer, B. (2021). A study of the relationship between secondary school students' computational thinking skills and creative problem-solving skills. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 20, 1-15.
- Phillips, P. (2009). Computational Thinking. a problem-solving tool for every classroom. *Communications of the CSTA*, 3(6). 12-16.
- Romero, M., Lepage, A., & Lille, B. (2017). Computational thinking development through creative programming in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*. Article 42 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0080-z>
- Rose, A. (2011). *Restorative environments influence on cognitive flexibility in developing adults*. Master Thesis. The University of Utah. <https://collections.lib.utah.edu/ark:/87278/s6p56373>
- Salamanca Garay, I. J. & Badilla Quintana, M. G. (2021). From computational thinking to creative thinking. an analysis of their relationship in high school students. *Icono 14*, 19(2), 261-285.
- Shah, J. Y., (2003). How representations of significant others implicitly, Automatic for the people Affect goal pursuit. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 84(38), 388-402.
- Tedre, M. & Denning, P. (2016). The long quest for computational thinking. *Proceedings of the 16th Koli Calling International Conference on Computing Education Research*, 120-129. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2999541.2999542>
- Voogt, J., Fisser, P., Good, J., Mishra, P., & Yadav, A., (2015). Computational thinking in compulsory education. Towards an agenda for research and practice. *Education and Information Technologies*, 20(4), 715-728. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-015-9412-6>
- Walliman, G. (2015). *Genost: A system for introductory computer science education with a focus on computational thinking*. A Thesis Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree Masters of Science. Arizona State University.

- Weinberg, A. E. (2013). *Computational thinking: An investigation of the existing scholarship and research*. In partial fulfillment of the requirements For the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy Colorado State University Fort Collins. Colorado.
- Weintrop, D., Beheshti, E., Horn, M., Orton, K., Jona, K., Trouille, L., & Wilensky, U. (2015). Defining computational thinking for mathematics and science classrooms. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 1–21
- Yadav, A., Mayfield, C., Zhou, N., Hambrusch, S., & Korb, J. T. (2014, March). Computational thinking in elementary and secondary teacher education. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education*, 14(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2576872>
- Yadav, A., Zhou, N., Mayfield, C., Hambrusch, S., & Korb, J. T., (2011). Introducing computational thinking in education courses. *In Proceedings of ACM Special Interest Group on Computer Science Education*. Dallas